

Strike Action and Academic Performance: A study of Niger Delta University

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of strike action on the academic performance of students at Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa. The study adopted the Tyler rational planning approach and the pluralist approach to industrial conflict. The cross-sectional design was adopted, and a questionnaire was used as the instrument to collect primary data. A multi-stage sampling technique was utilized for the study. The response rate of two hundred and seventeen (217) was analyzed with descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and bar chart) and inferential statistics such as Chi-Square at the $P < 0.05$ level of significance. The study established that there was a high prevalence of strike action in Niger Delta University, students study morale was dampened during strike action by the Academic Staff Union, and a high failure rate was reported for examinations written after strike action. Strike action had a direct negative effect on the cumulative grade point average (CGPA) of students, among others. The study recommended an upward review of Niger Delta University subvention policy/budgetary allocation and a proactive approach to addressing workers grievances through dialogue. Above all, the study suggested that the Academic Staff Union of Universities should adopt an approach that will have fewer negative effects on the academic performance of students in registering their grievances.

Keywords: Strike Action, CGPA, Academic Performance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Industrial action, commonly known as a strike, has become a frequent way for workers and organizations to express dissatisfaction with employers or the government. Ivancevich (2007) defines a strike as a tactic used by employees to withhold work to force employers into offering better terms. Strikes, however, are often viewed as harmful to all involved—employees, employers, students, parents, and the economy (Kawugana, 2016). In Nigerian universities, strikes have become a regular occurrence, disrupting academic activities. Students bear the brunt of these disruptions, as they are either left idle on campus or sent home indefinitely.

The root cause of strikes in Nigerian universities is the government's failure to honour agreements, particularly the 2009 agreement with the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). The poor condition of universities, reflected in inadequate funding, insufficient infrastructure, and low global rankings, leads to frequent strikes. Scholars like Olukoju (2002) and Ezekwesili (2006) have questioned why Nigeria, with its oil wealth, fails to adequately fund its universities. According to the World Bank (2013), Nigeria's resource wealth has not translated into improved welfare for its citizens.

Nigerian universities aim to produce graduates of high moral and academic standing (Amadi and Urho, 2015). However, the incessant strikes have led to a decline in the quality of education (Kagbaranen, 2012). These disruptions extend students' study years, strain teacher-student relationships, and negatively affect students' learning (Edinyang and Ubi, 2013).

For students at Niger Delta University, these disruptions are particularly demotivating, pushing them toward non-academic activities such as cyber fraud and gambling during strike periods (Chijioke, 2013, in Omotere, 2014). Research shows that prolonged strikes hinder students' ability to effectively cover their course syllabi, which impacts their academic performance (Odubela, 2012, in Omotere, 2014).

The long-term effects of strikes include emotional instability and poor academic performance for students (Isangedighi, 2007). Since ASUU's first strike in 1988, underfunding has remained a persistent issue, leading to a cycle of strikes that continues to disrupt Nigerian universities (Olusegun, 2014). To prevent further damage, it is essential for the government to honour its agreements with ASUU and ensure sufficient funding for the education sector.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Strike Actions and Academic Performance

Reviewing existing studies helps identify knowledge gaps that can be addressed by new research. Edinyang and Ubi (2013) conducted an empirical study on the impact of strike action on human development among social studies students in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. They aimed to assess how disruptions in academic programs due to strikes affect students' learning. Using a survey inferential research design, they found that strikes lead to school closures, resulting in extended study years and negative effects on students' development.

Osuorji and David (2014) investigated the impact of frequent strikes on business education students at Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria. Their study used a descriptive survey design to examine how strikes affect students' academic performance. The results showed that frequent strikes by lecturers negatively impacted the performance of business education students.

Similarly, Olaniyi and Aina (2014) explored the effects of incessant strikes on business education programs. Their analysis concluded that the failure to resolve strike-related challenges would exacerbate the underlying problems in Nigeria's education system. Ayeni and Kolawole (2014) also studied the effects of strikes on the achievement of goals in business education in Ekiti State tertiary institutions. They found that frequent strikes contributed to mass failure among students and concluded that ineffective personnel policies and management's lack of sincerity contributed to the persistent conflicts.

Olupayimo (2014) examined the impact of strikes on skill acquisition in business education. The study adopted a survey approach and concluded that strikes negatively affected skill acquisition process in business education programs, as strikes had become common in Nigeria's educational system. Strikes, the study noted, hindered students from acquiring essential skills.

Baker (2013) explored the effects of industrial action on student achievement in Canadian schools, focusing on grade 3 and 6 students in math, reading, and writing. The study used data from the Education Quality and Accountability Office (EQAO) and found that teacher strikes in grade 5 or 6 negatively impacted students' test score growth between grades 3 and 6. Similarly, Gabrielle Wills (2014) investigated the effects of teacher strikes on student learning in South African primary schools. Using cross-sectional analysis, the study concluded that teacher strikes had adverse effects on student learning.

In summary, existing studies highlight the detrimental effects of strikes on education, but none have used Ex-Post Facto Analysis or focused on Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State. Most

studies have employed descriptive or inferential survey designs without using Grade Point Average (GPA) as a measure of academic performance, except for a few works like Baker (2013) and Wills (2014), whose studies focused on Canada and South Africa, respectively. This gap presents an opportunity for further research using alternative methodologies and focusing on different educational contexts, such as Niger Delta University.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study utilizes two key theoretical frameworks—Tyler’s Rational Planning Approach and Pluralist Approach to Industrial Conflict—to analyse the impact of strike actions on academic performance at Niger Delta University. These frameworks provide complementary perspectives on the relationship between educational objectives and industrial disputes within university settings.

Tyler’s Rational Planning Approach

Tyler’s Rational Planning Approach, also known as the Objective Approach, is a well-established educational theory that emphasizes the achievement of predefined educational outcomes. This approach was pioneered by Ralph Tyler, a prominent American educator, in his book *Basic Principles of Curriculum and Instruction* (1949). Tyler’s theory focuses on the systematic design and planning of the curriculum with the explicit purpose of achieving specific educational objectives. The approach centres on the idea that education is a purposeful and intentional activity, and the primary goal is to achieve well-defined learning outcomes.

One of the core assumptions of this theory is that schools are purposeful institutions where educational activities are goal-directed and should not be disrupted by internal or external factors, such as strikes or industrial disputes. Tyler argues that rational activities, including education, are characterized by clear objectives, procedures, and expected outcomes, and the curriculum must be designed to meet these objectives (Igwe, 2000). In this context, the success of education is measured by changes in learners’ behaviour, which is directly influenced by their attention, commitment, and the stability of the learning environment.

A key premise of Tyler’s approach is that the ends (educational goals) justify the means, meaning that all efforts should be directed towards achieving the academic objectives of students. Disruptions, such as staff union strikes, are seen as major obstacles that impede students from reaching these objectives. Strikes interrupt the continuous process of education, delaying learning activities and compromising the overall academic performance of students (Aremu, Salako, Lawrence, and Ayelotan, 2015). According to this framework, the smooth running of educational institutions is crucial for ensuring that students meet the goals outlined in the curriculum.

However, Tyler’s Rational Planning Approach has been criticized for its narrow focus on outcomes while overlooking the broader social, political, and economic contexts that shape the educational environment. Critics argue that the theory does not consider structural factors, such as insufficient funding, poor infrastructure, or socio-economic inequalities, which often lead to strike actions in universities (Akume and Abdullahi, 2013). Despite these limitations, Tyler’s theory is relevant to this study because it provides a lens through which to understand how disruptions in the learning process, caused by strikes, directly affect students’ ability to meet academic goals.

The Pluralist Approach to Industrial Conflict

The pluralist approach to industrial Conflict offers a contrasting perspective that focuses on the workplace as a site of diverse and competing interests. This theory, developed by scholars such as John Dunlop (1958) and Alan Flanders (1965), suggests that industrial organizations, including universities, are composed of multiple groups with different ideologies and objectives. In the context of this study, these groups include university management, academic and non-academic staff, and students. According to the pluralist approach, conflict is an inherent and inevitable feature of industrial relations due to the differing goals and interests of these groups.

A central assumption of the pluralist theory is that workplace conflicts must be managed through negotiation and compromise rather than being seen as avoidable disruptions. The theory emphasizes the

role of collective bargaining as the primary mechanism through which these conflicts are resolved. Trade unions, in particular, are viewed as legitimate representatives of employees' interests, with the right to challenge management decisions and advocate for better working conditions (Budd, Gomez, and Meltz, 2004). This is highly relevant to the university setting, where academic staff unions play a pivotal role in negotiating with management over issues such as salaries, working conditions, and academic policies.

The Pluralist Approach also asserts that industrial conflict, while disruptive, can be regulated and contained through institutional mechanisms such as collective bargaining. In this context, strikes are seen as a reflection of unresolved tensions between university staff and management, but they also serve as an avenue for addressing grievances. The theory underscores the importance of finding a balance between the competing interests of management and labour, as both sides are necessary for the smooth functioning of the institution.

In applying the pluralist theory to this study, industrial conflict in Nigerian universities, such as staff union strikes, can be understood as a normal outcome of the competing interests between management and staff. Strikes emerge when collective bargaining fails to resolve disputes, but they also offer a way for staff to express dissatisfaction and demand better conditions. This theory is relevant in examining how these conflicts, though inevitable, impact the academic environment and, by extension, student performance. The theory also provides insight into the importance of effective industrial relations systems that can mediate between conflicting interests to minimize disruptions in the educational process.

While the pluralist approach recognizes the legitimacy of trade unions and their role in industrial relations, it has been criticized for being overly focused on formal mechanisms such as collective bargaining without adequately addressing the power imbalances between management and employees. Critics argue that the theory assumes a level playing field in negotiations, which may not always be the case in real-world scenarios, especially in contexts where management holds significant power over the terms of employment (Commons, 1957). Nonetheless, the pluralist approach remains a useful framework for this study as it helps explain the dynamics of industrial conflict in universities and its implications for academic performance.

In conclusion, both Tyler's Rational Planning Approach and the Pluralist Approach to Industrial Conflict offer valuable insights into the relationship between educational objectives and industrial action. While Tyler's approach emphasizes the importance of achieving academic goals and the negative impact of disruptions, the pluralist theory highlights the inevitability of conflict in diverse organizations and the role of collective bargaining in managing these disputes. Together, these frameworks provide a comprehensive understanding of how strike actions affect academic performance at Niger Delta University.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the Tyler rational planning approach and the pluralist approach to industrial conflict. The cross-sectional design was adopted, and a questionnaire was used as the instrument to collect primary data. The research questionnaire was administered to three hundred and ninety (390) respondents, which is the sample size representing the study population. Out of this lot, two hundred and seventeen (217) copies of the questionnaire representing (55.6%) were returned, and one hundred and seventy-three (173) copies of the questionnaire representing (44.4%) were not returned.

A multi-stage sampling technique was utilized for the study. The response rate of two hundred and seventeen (217) was analyzed with descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and bar chart) and inferential statistics such as Chi-Square at the $P < 0.05$ level of significance.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 Analysis of Response Rate

Copies of Questionnaire	F=390	P=100.0	CF=100.0
Returned	217	55.6	55.6

Not Returned	173	44.4	100.0
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Source: Field work (2024)

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Fig. 4.1 Analysis of Response Rate

Table 4.2 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	F=217	P=100.0	CF=100.0
Sex:			
Male	71	32.7	32.7
Female	146	67.3	100.0
Leve:			
100L	31	14.3	14.3
200L	21	9.7	24.0
300L	78	35.9	59.9
400L	37	17.1	77.0
500L	26	12.0	88.9
600L	24	11.1	100.0
Age:			
18-22	22	10.1	10.1
23-27	126	58.1	68.2
28-32	30	13.8	82.0
33-37	29	13.4	95.4
38>	10	4.6	100.0
CGPA:			
1.50-2.49	7	3.2	3.2
2.50-3.49	99	45.6	48.8
3.50-4.49	102	47.0	95.9

4.50-5.00	9	4.1	100.0
Faculty:			
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Ar			
Basic Medical Science	11	5.1	26.3
Clinical Science	12	5.5	31.8
Education Engineering	17	7.8	39.6
Management Science	23	10.6	50.2
Science	18	8.3	58.5
Social Science	18	8.3	66.8
Nursing	44	20.3	87.1
Pharmacy	5	2.3	89.4
Law	15	6.9	96.3
	8	3.7	100.0

Source: Field Work (2024).

The table above presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The findings reveal that 71 (32.7%) of respondents are male, while 146 (67.3%) are female, indicating that the majority (67.3%) of respondents are female. Regarding academic levels, 31 (14.3%) are in 100 level, 21 (9.7%) in 200 level, 78 (35.9%) in 300 level, 37 (17.1%) in 400 level, 26 (12.0%) in 500 level, and 24 (11.1%) in 600 level. Most respondents (35.9%) are in the 300 level.

In terms of age, 22 (10.1%) of students are between 18 and 22 years, 126 (58.1%) are between 23 and 27 years, 30 (13.8%) fall within 28 and 32 years, 29 (13.4%) are between 33 and 37 years, and 10 (4.6%) are 38 years and above. The majority (58.1%) are between 23 and 27 years.

Regarding cumulative grade point average (CGPA), 7 (3.2%) have a CGPA of 1.50-2.49, 99 (45.6%) have 2.50-3.49, 102 (47.0%) have 3.50-4.49, and 9 (4.1%) have a CGPA of 4.50-5.00.

Finally, the faculty distribution shows that 37 (17.1%) are in agriculture, 9 (4.1%) in arts, 11 (5.1%) in basic medical science, 12 (5.5%) in clinical science, 17 (7.8%) in education, 23 (10.6%) in engineering, 18 (8.3%) in management science, 18 (8.3%) in science, 44 (20.3%) in social sciences, 5 (2.3%) in Nursing, 15 (6.9%) in Pharmacy, and 8 (3.7%) in Law. The majority (20.3%) are in the Faculty of Social Sciences.

Table 4.3 Trends of Strike Action in Niger Delta University

Variables	F=217	P=100.0	CF=100.0	\bar{x}
Experience of strike action in NDU	¹ Yes=175	80.6	80.6	1.1(1.0)
	² No=42	19.4	100.0	
How often do you experience strikes in NDU?	¹ Not at all = 77	3.2	3.2	3.4(1.8)
	² Rarely=21	9.7	12.9	
	³ Often=60	27.6	40.6	
	⁴ Very often=129	59.4	100.0	
Nature of strike action in NDU	¹ ASUU=177	81.6	81.6	1.2(1.0)
	² NASUU=40	18.4	100.0	
NDU calendar before strike action	¹ Very slow=13	6.0	6.0	3.0(1.7)
	² Slow=33	15.2	21.2	
	³ Fast=108	49.8	71.0	
	⁴ Very fast=63	29.0	100.0	
Duration of the last strike action in NDU	¹ <1month=6	2.8	2.8	2.9(1.7)
	² 2-4months=48	22.1	24.9	

The table above shows strike action trends in Niger Delta University. According to the results, 175 (80.6%) of students experienced strike action, while 42 (19.4%) did not. A majority, 129 (59.4%), experienced strike action "very often," while 7 (3.2%) said "not at all," 21 (9.7%) reported "rarely," and 60 (27.6%) said "often."

When asked about the type of strike, most respondents (177 = 81.6%) indicated ASUU, while 40 (18.4%) indicated NASUU. The strikes affected the academic calendar, with 108 (49.8%) stating that the calendar was fast before the strike. Regarding strike duration, the majority (78.8%) reported that the last strike lasted 5-7 months, followed by 48 (22.1%) reporting 2-4 months, 46 (21.2%) reporting 8 months, and 6 (2.8%) indicating less than a month.

Table 4.4 Causes of Strike Action at Niger Delta University

Variables	F=217	P=100.0	CF=100.0	\bar{x}
Government response to strike action in NDU	¹ Proactive=25	11.5	11.5	1.9(1.4)
	² Reactive=192	88.5	100.0	
Nonpayment of workers salary causes strike action in NDU	¹ Strongly = 78	3.7	3.7	3.2(1.8)
		10.1	13.8	
		50.2	64.1	
		35.9	100.0	
Relationship between NDU staffs and management	¹ Not cordial=39	18.0	18.0	2.7(1.6)
	² Fairly cordial=46	21.2	39.2	
	³ Cordial=70	32.3	71.4	
	⁴ Very cordial=62	28.6	100.0	
Subvention policy cause untimely payment of workers salary in NDU	¹ Strongly agree=26	4.1	4.1	2.8(1.7)
		22.6	26.7	
		61.3	88.0	
		12.0	100.0	

Source: Field Work (2024).

The table above highlights the causes of strike action in Niger Delta University. The findings reveal that 192 (88.5%) of respondents believe the government's response to strike action is reactive, while 25 (11.5%) consider it proactive. Regarding the nonpayment of workers' salaries as a cause of strikes, 109 (50.2%) agreed, 78 (35.9%) strongly agreed, 22 (10.1%) disagreed, and 8 (3.7%) strongly disagreed. Thus, a majority (50.2%) agree that salary nonpayment leads to strikes.

In terms of the relationship between staff and management, 39 (18.0%) rated it as "not cordial," 46 (21.2%) as "fairly cordial," 70 (32.3%) as "cordial," and 62 (28.6%) as "very cordial." Most respondents (32.3%) described the relationship as cordial. Lastly, the analysis showed that the subvention policy affects salary payments, with a mean score of 2.8 and a standard deviation of 1.7.

Table 4.4 Strike Action and Academic Performance in Niger Delta University

Strike Action		Cumulative Grade Point Average					Cross-Tab
		1.50-2.49	2.50-3.49	3.50-4.49	4.50-5.0		
NDU calendar before strike action	VS	0(0.0)	50(23.0)	26(12.0)	7(3.2)	83(38.2)	$\chi^2=51.384$ Df=9 Sig.= 0.000*
	S	6(2.8)	34(15.7)	74(34.1)	0(0.0)	114(52.5)	
	F	1(0.5)	8(3.7)	2(0.9)	2(0.9)	13(6.0)	
	VF	0(0.0)	7(3.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	7(3.2)	
		7(3.2)	99(45.6)	102(47.0)	9(4.1)	217(100.0)	
Study morale during strike action in NDU	VL	0(0.0)	3(1.4)	34(15.7)	7(3.2)	44(20.3)	$\chi^2=155.537$ Df=9 Sig.= 0.000*
	L	7(3.2)	96(44.2)	18(8.3)	2(0.9)	123(56.7)	
	H	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	39(18.0)	0(0.0)	39(18.0)	
	VH	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	11(5.1)	0(0.0)	11(5.1)	
		7(3.2)	99(45.6)	102(47.0)	9(4.1)	217(100.0)	
Level of academic satisfaction	VD	1(0.5)	21(9.7)	37(17.1)	9(4.1)	68(31.3)	$\chi^2=43.854$ Df=9 Sig.= 0.000*
	D	6(2.8)	67(30.9)	45(20.7)	0(0.0)	118(54.4)	
	S	0(0.0)	11(5.1)	9(4.1)	0(0.0)	20(9.2)	
	VS	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	11(5.1)	0(0.0)	11(5.1)	
		7(3.2)	99(45.6)	102(47.0)	9(4.1)	217(100.0)	
Likelihood of strike action in NDU	SD	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(1.4)	0(0.0)	3(1.4)	$\chi^2=81.477$ Df=9 Sig.= 0.000*
	D	6(2.8)	37(17.1)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	43(19.8)	
	A	1(0.05)	41(18.9)	39(18.0)	2(0.9)	83(38.2)	
	SA	0(0.0)	21(9.7)	60(27.6)	7(3.2)	88(40.6)	
		7(3.2)	99(45.6)	102(47.0)	9(4.1)	217(100.0)	
$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum(X)}{n}$ $\bar{x} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4}$ $\bar{x} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$		VS = Very Slow, S = Slow, F = Fast ³ , VF = Very Fast ⁴ , VH = Very High. H=High ³ , VH=Very High ⁴ , VD=Very Dissatisfied ¹ , D=Dissatisfied ² , VS = Very satisfied. SD=Strongly Disagree ¹ , D=Disagree ² , SA = strongly agree ⁴ .					

Source: Field Work (2024).

The table above presents a cross-tabulation of strike actions and students' academic performance at Niger Delta University. Findings reveal that 50 (23.0%) of students with a CGPA of 2.50-3.49 rated the academic calendar as "very slow" before the strike, along with 26 (12.0%) of students with a CGPA of 3.50-4.49 and 7 (3.2%) with a CGPA of 4.50-5.00. A total of 144 (66.4%) students described the calendar as either "slow" or "very slow."

Analysis shows a significant relationship between the school calendar and cumulative grade point average (CGPA) ($\chi^2 = 51.384$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.000$). Additionally, there is a relationship between study morale

during strike action and CGPA ($\chi^2 = 155.537$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.000$). For instance, students with low morale during strikes mostly had CGPAs between 2.50 and 3.49, with few attaining higher results.

Furthermore, academic satisfaction impacts CGPA ($\chi^2 = 43.854$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.000$). Of students who were "very dissatisfied," 31.3% had CGPAs below 3.50. Lastly, analysis showed that the likelihood of future

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Table 4.5 Perception of Students Towards Strike Action in Niger Delta University

Variables	F=217	P=100.0	CF=100.0	\bar{x}
How worried are you that NDU is likely to go on strike	¹ Not worried at all = 3	1.4	1.4	3.2(1.8)
	² Not too worried = 43	19.8	21.2	
	³ Somewhat worried=83	38.2	59.4	
	⁴ Very worried=88	40.6	100.0	
Have you ever felt like abandoning study due to strike action in NDU	¹ None of the time = 7	3.2	3.2	3.2(1.8)
	² A little of timetime = 344	15.7	18.9	
	³ Most of the time=91	41.9	60.8	
	⁴ All of the time = 85	39.2	100.0	
How important is it for NDU not to go on strike	¹ Not important=5	2.3	2.3	3.2(1.8)
	² Slightly important=8	3.7	6.0	
	³ Important=147	67.7	73.7	
	⁴ Very important=57	26.3	100.0	

Source: Field Work (2024).

The table presents students' perceptions of strike actions at Niger Delta University. The majority, 88 (40.6%), reported feeling "very worried" about strike actions, while 83 (38.2%) were "somewhat worried." Only 3 (1.4%) were "not worried at all." Most students, 91 (41.9%), felt like abandoning their studies "most of the time," and 85 (39.2%) felt this way "all of the time," with just 7 (3.2%) never considering it.

Furthermore, 147 (67.7%) of respondents stated that it is "important" for the university to avoid strikes, while 57 (26.3%) rated it "very important." Only a few, 5 (2.3%), considered it "not important."

Table 4.6 Methods of Resolving Strike Action in Niger Delta University

Variables	F=217	P=100.0	CF=100.0	\bar{x}
How probable is it for strike to be resolved through dialogue	¹ Very improbable=9	4.1	4.1	2.9(1.7)
	² Improbable= 69	31.8	35.9	
	³ Probable=65	30.0	65.9	
	⁴ Very probable=74	34.1	100.0	
Prompt payment of workers salary reduce strike	¹ Strongly disagree=2	0.9	9	3.6(1.9)
	² Disagree=3	1.4	2.3	
	³ Agree=80	36.9	39.2	
	⁴ Strongly Agree=132	60.8	100.0	
Implementation of MoU reduce strike in NDU	¹ Strongly disagree=4	1.8	1.8	3.3(1.8)
	² Disagree=14	6.5	8.3	
	³ Agree=106	48.8	57.1	
	⁴ Strongly agree=93	42.9	100.0	

Source: Field Work (2024).

The table above outlines methods of resolving strike actions at Niger Delta University. A mean score of 2.9 (SD = 1.7) was reported for those who found dialogue likely to resolve strikes. The majority, 74 (34.1%), indicated it was "very probable," while 69 (31.8%) found it "improbable."

Regarding prompt payment of salaries, the analysis revealed a high mean score of 3.6 (SD = 1.9), with 132 (60.8%) strongly agreeing it would reduce strikes. Similarly, the implementation of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) scored a mean of 3.3 (SD = 1.8), with 93 (42.9%) strongly agreeing it would help prevent strikes.

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Testing Hypothesis

H01 There is no significant relationship between strike action and cumulative grade point average of students in Niger Delta University.

Table 4.7 Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria			Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	AIC of Reduced Model	BIC of Reduced Model	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	25.140	45.419	13.140 ^a	.000	0	.
Strike	103.754	113.893	97.754	84.614	3	.000
Observed and Predicted Frequencies						
Have you experienced strikes in NDU?	CGPA	Frequency			Percentage	
		Observed	Predicted	Pearson Residual	Observed	Predicted
Yes	1.50-2.49	0	.000	-.002	0.0%	0.0%
	2.50-3.49	64	64.000		36.6%	36.6%
	3.50-4.49	102	102.000		58.3%	58.3%
	4.50-5.00	9	9.000		5.1%	5.1%
No	1.50-2.49	7	7.000	.000	16.7%	16.7%
	2.50-3.49	35	35.000		83.3%	83.3%
	3.50-4.49	0	.000		0.0%	0.0%
	4.50-5.00	0	.000		0.0%	0.0%

The percentages are based on total observed frequencies in each subpopulation.

Source: Field Work (2024).

The table above shows the observed and predicted frequencies of dependent and independent variables. Chi-square was used to test the effects of strike action on cumulative grade point average; when this was done, analysis showed ($\chi^2 = 84.614$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.000$). Therefore, the null hypothesis will be rejected, while the alternate hypothesis, which holds that there is a significant relationship between strike action and the cumulative grade point average of students at Niger Delta University, will be accepted.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study found that most respondents had a cumulative grade point average of 3.50–4.49, indicating second-class upper division status. Despite this, strike actions at Niger Delta University were infrequent, suggesting that strikes were familiar to students. The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) frequently initiated these strikes, which disrupted academic activities, with the last one lasting about 5–7 months. The government's response to strikes was identified as reactive rather than proactive, highlighting the need for measures to prevent future strikes. Non-payment of salaries was a key factor triggering strike actions, and the subvention policy had negatively impacted the university's revenue.

After the strike, the academic calendar slowed significantly, adversely affecting students' GPAs. Low study morale during strikes also correlated with lower academic performance and increased student anxiety regarding potential strikes, leading many to consider abandoning their studies. The findings stressed the importance of avoiding strikes due to their impact on the academic calendar. Dialogue was identified as the most effective resolution method, along with prompt salary payments and the im

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CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, the study concludes that strike action had a negative effect on the academic performance of students at Niger Delta University during the period under review. The study also concludes that cumulative grade point average, study morals, and level of academic satisfaction among students in Niger Delta University decline during strike action.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the above submission, the study recommends as follows:

- Bayelsa State government should review her subvention policy at Niger Delta University. Thus, budgetary allocation to the state premiere university should be reviewed upward so as to ensure that workers' salaries are paid when due.
- Bayelsa State government should be proactive in managing industrial conflict. There is no gain for the continual practice of reactive approach while responding to strike action.
- Dialogue remains the major tool in addressing strike action. Thus, aggrieved parties should cultivate the culture of dialogue while managing strike action.
- Considering the negative effects of strike action on the cumulative grade point average (CGPA) of students, labour unions in Niger Delta University (ASUU & NASUU) should explore other student grievance resolution mechanisms in addressing grievance and not the anachronistic strike action.

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